

INFLUENCE OF RESOURCE ALLOCATION ON PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION BY BUSIA COUNTY GOVERNMENT, KENYA

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Abstract: Kenya's county governments each have their own arrangement of necessities and difficulties when it comes to health care. The construction of health care facilities program in Busia County, funded by various sources, As a result, the number of health facilities in all sub-counties has increased. The County Government has made significant improvements to the health-care infrastructure. These projects, however, face implementation challenges, as many health projects fail to be implemented due to factors such as time inefficiency, financial constraints, and a lack of political will. Therefore, the study sought to investigate the influence of resource allocation on the implementation of health care projects by Busia County Government, Kenya. A descriptive research approach was used. The unit of analysis was six health projects implemented by Busia County, Kenya. The unit of observation will be 95 respondents, who were project managers and team members. A census of 95 respondents was conducted. The study instrument was a questionnaire. To analyze quantitative data, descriptive statistics using means and standard deviations were adopted. The presentation of data was in tables and figures. The inferential statistics that involved correlation and regressions analysis was used to determine the influence of one variable on the other. The study found that resource allocation had a positive and significant influence on projects implementation by Busia County government, Kenya. The study concluded that proper allocation of resource ensures that the project has the right staff, equipment, money, etc. as efficiently as possible and helps the project manager to identify problems, avoid over allocation and adapt to change. The study recommended that the project managers must ensure the right number of project team members are available at any given time and must also know they have to avoid overstaffing and understaffing.

Keywords: Resource Allocation, Project Implementation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Project management includes project planning and project implementation, as well as planning, directing, and managing corporate resources for a short period goal of completing specific goals and objectives (Ntamere, 2015). The implementation of projects is one of the tools used in managing change in organizations. Implementation is used by project managers making structured changes in associations by establishing conditions where change can get by and grow. From this vantage point, execution can be considered an interaction utilized in arranging a change cycle that sets out the means taken by all partners to help change. As a result, the project manager is responsible for controlling the company's resources in terms of time, cost, and performance in order to effectively implement a project.

A number of bottlenecks with cross-cutting effects exist in the global implementation of projects. For example, Khan, Turner, and Maqsood (2019) state that development achievements. The achievement of a country's objectives is primarily dependent on the implementation of development projects. In Pakistan, a portion of development projects are delayed due to cost and time overruns, which must be improved through an integrated and comprehensive strategy. As a result, a

comprehensive, multifaceted strategy is required to manage project delays, which have a number of negative consequences such as suboptimal use of funds, opportunity cost, political leverage of the government, socioeconomic development at the local and national levels, and misalignment with international development goals.

The case of erratic project implementation is not unique in the region. Many Sub-Saharan African countries are losing billions of dollars as a result of the slow completion of infrastructure programs, undermining the admirable mission of poverty reduction (Gutman et al., 2015). In Africa, infrastructure projects are a critical catalyst for increasing a country's productivity and assisting the continent's integration into the global economy, as well as supporting long-term growth and socially holistic financial progress. According to Odeyinka and Yusif (2010), seven out of ten Nigerian projects surveyed experienced implementation delays. Over the last 15 years, Tanzania has embarked on a series of initiatives and project implementation efforts that have resulted in significant improvements in the region's growth practices. As a result, significant programs in the Zanzibar Islands and Tanzania's mainland have been funded and launched (Tsekpo & Hudson, 2012).

According to Amade, Ogbonna, and Kaduru (2018), in the outcome of task execution, ecological elements are more significant than the skill portfolio of the project team at six project sites in Anambra, Imo, and River States. The capability of project managers to create exact plans, quotes, and time evaluations will limit the adverse consequences of financial uncertainty on effective delivery of projects. Therefore, adequate environmental scanning, monitoring, and evaluation are required during project planning.

According to Kogi (2018), the effective implementation of projects carried out by the Nairobi County project is heavily influenced with funding levels, project cost management, and project planning, and recommends that exact undertaking gauges be finished toward the start of the project. Kariithi and Mbugua (2018), on the other hand, show that project funding and political factors have significantly influenced the implementation of a development project in Kiambu County, and they suggest that counties in Kenya should make better budgetary allocations for projects to ensure full implementation.

The implementation phase involves developing a project plan. A project is thought of as effective whenever finished on time, on a careful spending plan premise, and meets or exceeds nearly all of the original objectives, as well as being approved and used by customers designed for them (Mbaluku & Bwisa, 2013). Ideally, project implementation is an endeavor undertaken by individuals who collaborate to develop a new product or service within the stipulated time and budget in order to achieve identifiable deliverables (Project Management Institute, 2013). Most construction projects face significant challenges in terms of time and cost management. This results in a failure to complete the project within the time frame specified, which raises the costs involved. Because of numerous failed project implementations, the intended benefits are only partially or never realized.

Meredith, Shafer, and Mantel (2017) state that resources, whether people, money, hardware, or something else, are required throughout the project development process. Every project manager should monitor the use of resources trends and must plan the exact amounts of resources required for the entire project based on experience and available inputs. According to Sepulveda, Godue, Padilla, and Vidaurre (2019), it is critical to properly manage a project's resources in order to ensure its success. Everything ends up affecting the effectiveness of project implementation if resources are not managed effectively. As a result, any increase or decrease in resources directly impacts the project's budget as well as its timeline.

Busia County is located in western Kenya and serves as a gateway to Kenya's regional neighbors with two border crossing points located in Busia and Malaba Towns. Under Infrastructure Development, the department completed the accident and emergency block at Busia County Referral Hospital and has already put a portion of the building to use. The ground floor, which serves as the casualty area, is currently used to review patients from special clinics, while the third floor, which serves as the administrative area, is used for board meetings and other engagements. The ICU equipment was also installed on the first floor of the building, while waiting servicing (tendering is still ongoing), and later on ICU services will be launched to provide this vital service to the residents of Busia. Other projects, including the Kenya Devolution Support Programme (KDSP), have also made significant progress. Among these was the completion of Kocholiya Hospital's 30-bed Male Medical Ward in Teso North Sub County. In the same facility, a ward was also converted into a cutting-edge laboratory. Significant progress has also been made toward the completion of the Maternity and Newborn Unit at Port Victoria Hospital in Bunyala, which will soon be ready for commissioning. The Referral Hospital has also received a major facelift, including the installation of cabro works at the hospital parking bay, the improvement of walkways, and the construction of a modern gate, among other things.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Completing projects on time has a huge impact to an organization's competitive edge. This is based on the perception that the ability to deliver output is targeted within the specified time frame determines achievement of the targeted objectives (Kariungi, 2014). Healthcare projects in Busia's county governments each have their needs and challenges. For example, according to documents, Sydcas Construction Limited was awarded a one-year project to build a maternity unit at Busia County Referral Hospital from June 2014 to June 2015. However, as of June 2017, the county had paid Sh31.58 million despite no visible progress on the ground. The construction work was completed to a 40% level. According to the records, the Busia County Management pushed for the payment to be made despite the inability to complete the work according to the agreed-upon signed contract. Furthermore, an accident and emergency unit at Busia Referral Hospital has been halted. The white elephant project, which is now an eyesore, had cost Sh52.73 million. According to the Auditor General's Report, physical verification two and a half years after the planned completion date reveals that the work has stalled at 70% completion. Sh1.88 million in additional allowances paid to county officers has not been recovered.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

Penrose (1959) proposed a Resource Based View theory, which expresses that the firm is an assortment of monetary assets, HR and hierarchical assets. In theory, a unique fixed asset actually combines the company's power and control with the company to consolidate assets, allowing the company to create more market opportunities to contribute to its operations. In addition, the company can be considered as a set of skills and resources that allow it to continue to exist. Furthermore, within the corporate system, resources are regarded as the most important analysis unit. Furthermore, an organization may be given consideration utilizing a set of abilities and resources that allow it to continue to exist.

According to resource-based theory, this can be accomplished by embracing four critical processes: responding to external opportunities, transforming internal weaknesses into strengths, and developing and implementing an internal energy strategy. Embracing the culture of an organization that competitors can replicate; Developing specific human capital knowledge and abilities Organizations gain a competitive advantage through the vital power of inelastic supply and bulk resources (Mata, Fuerst & Barney, 1995; Afiouni, 2007). In line with resource-based theory, organizations should use all sources of competitive advantage with the goal of developing unique strategies to determine customer value (O'Sullivan, 2011).

According to studies, the competitive advantage basis is based on three assumptions: market management skills and technical risks are not static; when distributed in large quantities and separately to all competing firms, skills and resources can be an effective source of competition; and skills and resources can be a source of sustainable competitive profit firms available firms vary (Bordello, Ravarini, Wu & Nigam, 2012). This theory is important for research because it reflects the manner in which the County government accomplishes projects based on its resources and capabilities. To be a source for the successful implementation of their health resources projects must be distinctive.

Empirical Literature Review

Rugiri and Njangiru (2018) studied on the influence of resource allocation on water projects performance funded by Nyeri County, Kenya through CDF. Human capital and capital were used to calculate resource allocation. The population comprised of 86 water projects in Nyeri County that were CDF-funded. The researcher selected 60 respondents using a stratified random sample methodology, all of whom were project managers for water projects. Regression and correlation analysis were employed as well as bivariate and multivariate approaches, were used to find relevant findings. The regression analysis results also revealed that resource availability was a good predictor of project success. According to the findings of a Pearson correlation study, resource availability was positively related to project success.

Ndayisaba and Mulyungi (2018) studied on management of resources on the implementation of projects. Project to Strengthen Livelihoods in Rural Rwanda Time management, financial resources, and human resources were all used to assess resource allocation. All project participants were included in the target population. Analysis of data was quantitatively done through regression analysis so as to assess how the variables under study were related to one another. It was discovered that management of resources accounted for 83.7% influence on successful implementation of projects in strengthening livelihoods in rural Rwanda project Muhanga district.

Kimutai and Kirui (2020) investigated the impact of resource schedule on the implementation of residential building projects in Kenya. Task allocation and time management were used to assess resource allocation. The design employed was descriptive research. The population constituted of 79 residential projects and the respondents were the project managers, project supervisors, and contractors. Questionnaires were used in collecting data. The study discovered a link between resource scheduling and project implementation.

Ochieng (2018) investigated the impact of management of resources on the implementation of mobile communications companies projects in Kenya. Task scheduling and time allocation were used to assess resource management. The target population consisted of fifty project team members from Kenya's four major GSM companies. To demonstrate the relationship between the variables, descriptive statistics were used. The study also revealed that technology is still poorly managed, with a large proportion of respondents indicating that databases are managed manually and project management software is rarely used.

Hassani (2018) investigated the impact of resource allocation on implementation of primary schools' projects in Tanzania's Chamwino District. Scheduling and time allocation were used to assess resource management. The research utilized descriptive design in determining the relationship between variables. The population constituted of 115 respondents. The respondents were purposively chosen. A questionnaire was used in collecting data that was analysed descriptively and also using inferential statistics. The study's findings revealed that men contributed little to project implementation compared to women and youth who were concerned about project implementation.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research approach was used. The unit of analysis was six health projects implemented by Busia County, Kenya. The unit of observation will be 95 respondents, who were project managers and team members. A census of 95 respondents was conducted. The study instrument was a questionnaire. To analyze quantitative data, descriptive statistics using means and standard deviations were adopted. The presentation of data was in tables and figures. The inferential statistics that involved correlation and regressions analysis was used to determine the influence of one variable on the other.

4. FINDINGS

The descriptive statistics results of resource allocation are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Resource Allocation

Statement	M	SD
The County Government of Busia allocates sufficient funds to projects.	4.52	1.129
Delays in funding have slowed the pace of project implementation in Busia County.	4.79	0.768
The type of projects to be implemented in Busia County is determined by the level of funds allocated.	4.04	1.706
Busia County has a low rate of fund utilization.	4.67	0.597
Busia County has insufficient access to funding.	4.05	0.721
Busia County has insufficient resource mobilization.	4.29	1.098
Busia County suffers from a lack of project funding.	3.54	1.361

The respondents strongly agreed that delays in funding have slowed the pace of project implementation in Busia County (M=4.79, SD=0.768), Busia County has a low rate of fund utilization (M=4.67, SD=0.597) and that the County Government of Busia allocates sufficient funds to projects (M=4.52, SD=1.129). The finding is in concurrence with Sepulveda, Godue, Padilla, and Vidaurre (2019) who observe that it is critical to properly manage a project's resources in order to ensure its success.

The respondents agreed that Busia County has insufficient resource mobilization (M=4.29, SD=1.098), Busia County has insufficient access to funding (M=4.05, SD=0.721), the type of projects to be implemented in Busia County is determined by the level of funds allocated (M=4.04, SD=1.706) and that Busia County suffers from a lack of project funding (M=3.54, SD=1.361). The results are in consistent with Siborurema, Shukla and Mbera (2015) who observe that both the cost estimation and technical design interfere with the projects funding policy and affect negatively the scheduled projects implementation time.

Results of Inferential Statistics

Correlation analysis

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

		Resource allocation	Project implementation
Resource allocation	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
		N	
Project implementation performance	Pearson Correlation	.616**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
		N	91

With a Pearson's r value of 0.616, which is close to 1, and a significant value of 0.00, which is less than 0.05, the results in Table 2 demonstrate that the resource allocation had a significant relationship with the project implementation. This demonstrates a strong relationship, indicating that the Busia County government in Kenya's project implementation and resource allocation were closely related.

Results of Regression Analysis

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.872 ^a	0.729	0.716	1.233

According to the results in Table 3, the adjusted r squared value was 0.716 (71.6%), which means that, at a 95% confidence level, there was a variation in the project implementation by the Busia County government in Kenya of 71.6% that could be attributed to changes in resource allocation. This means that, aside from the resource allocation, variables not examined in this research contributed 27.1% of the variation in project implementation by the Busia County government in Kenya.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F.	Sig.
1	Regression	3.972	1	3.972	11.614	.000
	Residual	30.775	90	0.342		
	Total	34.747	91			

A significance value of 0.000 less than 0.05 was achieved. The F statistical value was also 11.614 higher than the 3.972 statistical mean square value. As a result, it was determined that the model was statistically significant in predicting how resource allocation had an impact on the Busia County government of Kenya's project implementation.

Table 5: Coefficient

Model		Unstandardised coefficients		Unstandardised coefficients		
		B	Sd.Err	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.744	.297		2.505	.000
1	Resource allocation	.877	.153	.163	5.732	.001

According to the regression equation established, taking all the resource allocation into constant, the project implementation by Busia County government, Kenya would be 0.744. The regression coefficient of resource allocation was 0.877 which indicates the extent to which project implementation is influenced by increasing a single unit in resource allocation.

Project implementation = 0.744 + 0.877 resource allocation

The study further established that the resource allocation had a positive and significant influence on project implementation by Busia County government, Kenya as indicated by beta value of 0.007 with a significance value less than 0.05 at 0.001.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that the project manager can identify issues, prevent overallocation, and adapt to change with the help of proper resource allocation, which guarantees that the project has the appropriate staff, equipment, money, etc., as efficiently as possible. The efficient use of the resources available and their distribution among various aspects of the projects are also ensured by proper resource allocation.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that the project managers must know they must avoid overstaffing and understaffing and make sure the appropriate number of project team members are available at all times. The County must take care to manage a sizable amount of equipment to be used during project implementation and adopt any new technology needed for the project's successful execution. The study suggested that County continually assess its financial situation to determine where money would be best spent on the project being carried out.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amade, B., Ogbonna, A., & Kaduru, C. (2018). Determinants of successful project implementation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 1(6), 56 – 69
- [2] Hassani, A. K. (2018). *Resource management and project implementation in selected primary schools in Chamwino District, Tanzania* (Kampala International University, Uganda)
- [3] Kariithi, W. K., & Mbugua, D. M. (2018). Factors influencing implementation of county development funded projects in Kenya: a case of Kiambu County. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Information Technology*, 4(5), 129-141
- [4] Kariungi, S. (2016). Determinants of timely completion of projects in Kenya: A Case of Kenya Power and Lighting Company, Thika. *ABC Journal of Advanced Research*, 3(2), 9 – 20
- [5] Khan, K., Turner, J. R., & Maqsood, T. (2019). Factors that influence the success of public sector projects in Pakistan. In *Proceedings of IRNOP 2013 Conference* (pp. 17-19).
- [6] Kogi, D. M. (2018). *Factors influencing the effectiveness of implementation of the economic stimulus programme (Esp). The case of construction projects in Nairobi County, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi)
- [7] Meredith, J. R., Shafer, S. M., & Mantel Jr, S. J. (2017). *Project management: a strategic managerial approach*. John Wiley & Sons
- [8] Ndayisaba, O., & Mulyungi, P. (2018). Effect of Resources Management on Project Success Implementation. A Case of Strengthening Livelihoods in Rural Rwanda Project. *International Journal of Research in Management, Economics and Commerce*, 8(5), 32–41.
- [9] Ntamere, C. C. (2015). *Project Management: Theory and Practice*. African-FebPublishers Ltd. Onitsha
- [10] Ochieng, E. A. (2018). *Influence of resource management on implementation of projects in global system of mobile communications companies in Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- [11] Penrose, E. T. (1959). *The Theory of the Growth of the Firm*. New York: John Wiley
- [12] Rugiri, M. N., & Njangiru, J. M. (2018). Effect of Resource Availability on Performance of Water Projects Funded by Constituency Development Fund In Nyeri County, Kenya. *International Academic Journal of Information Sciences and Project Management*, 3(2), 378–393
- [13] Sepulveda, H. R. Godue, C., Padilla, M., & Vidaurre, T. D. A. (2019). Assessment of human resources for health programme implementation in 15 Latin American and Caribbean countries. *Human resources for health*, 13(1), 1-9